

MicrobeSeq Denmark

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STATENS
SERUM
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Strengthened capacity and Sustainable Infrastructures for Sequencing based diagnostic preparedness

With financial support from the EU4Health programme, the SSI-Seq project will develop MicrobeSeq Denmark, a center dedicated to data sharing, communication, and standardisation of microbial WGS data in Denmark.

Aim

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) of microorganisms is of high importance in Danish infection surveillance and preparedness. MicrobeSeq Denmark will ensure that SSI and the Clinical Microbiology Departments in Denmark keep producing sequences of high quality and allow for the continuous improvement of data analysis and data sharing. To benefit as many as possible, computer codes will be open source and lab protocols will be made publicly available. It will be easy to share sequencing data with the rest of the EU.

How will this be obtained?

To ensure that WGS data for surveillance is of high and comparable quality, pipelines and workflows related to surveillance will be optimized and further developed.

This includes developing publicly available lab protocols, investigation of new lab methods and wet-lab training.

To allow for sharing WGS data and analysis results in as real-time as possible, IT infrastructures and bioinformatics tools will be developed.

This includes moving the system to a supercomputer, improvement of databases, development of new open source tools to analyze data, and bioinformatics training.

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